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CRITERIA FOR THE SELECTION OF TERMS DENOTING FAMILY TIES

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ANNOTATION

This article is devoted to the analysis of the terms of kinship and property based on dictionary definitions. This paper discusses various approaches to the study of these terms, their classification and criteria for their selection. Kinship determines social relations, determines the place of a person in society and corrects his behavior. Moreover, the terms of kinship and properties reflect the originality of the language, the specifics of the national path, and therefore characterize the national mentality.

Key words. Kinship, social relations, place of a person, society, marriage, kinship, gender-based terms are uncle, aunt, grandfather, grandmother.

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КРИТЕРИИ ОТБОРА ТЕРМИНОВ, ОБОЗНАЧАЮЩИХ РОДСТВЕННЫЕ СВЯЗИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Данная статья посвящена анализу терминов родства и их свойства на основе словарных определений. В данной работе рассматриваются различные подходы к изучению этих терминов, их классификация и критерии их выделения. Родство определяет общественные отношения, определяет место человека в обществе и корректирует его поведение. При этом термины родства и свойства отражают своеобразие языка, специфику национального пути и характеризуют национальный менталитет.

Ключевые слова. Родство, общественные отношения, место человека, общество, брак, родство, гендерные термины дядя, тетя, дедушка, бабушка.

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QARINDOSHLIK MUNOSABATLARINI BILDIRUVCHI ATAMALARNING SARALASH MEZONLARI

АННОТАЦИЯ

Ushbu maqola qarindoshlik va mulk atamalarini lug'at ta'riflari asosida tahlil qilishga bag'ishlangan. Ushbu maqolada ushbu atamalarni o'rganishga turli yondashuvlar, ularning tasnifi va ularni tanlash mezonlari muhokama qilinadi. Qarindoshlik ijtimoiy munosabatlarni belgilaydi, insonning jamiyatdagi o'rnini belgilaydi va uning xatti-harakatlarini to'g'rilaydi. Qolaversa, qarindoshlik va xususiyatlar atamaları tilning o'ziga xosligini, milliy yo'lning o'ziga xosligini aks ettiradi, shuning uchun ham milliy mentalitetni tavsiflaydi.

Kalit so'zlar. Qarindoshlik, ijtimoiy munosabatlar, shaxsning o'rnini, jamiyat, nikoh, qarindoshlik, jinsga asoslangan atamalar - amaki, xola, bobo, buvi.

Introduction. Kinship terminology is an important part of the vocabulary of any language. And there are two main approaches to the study of these terms. Firstly, kinship terms can only be considered as part of the vocabulary, that is, they are studied from a linguistic point of view. Secondly, this terminology can be the object of study of ethnology.

With this approach, kinship terms are studied in order to identify the features of ethno-cultural development, ethnic ties, and family and marriage norms.

Although, of course, the phenomena of kinship are also objects of study of such sciences as: biology, sociology, jurisprudence, cultural studies and others.

Depending on the angle, from the point of view of which science kinship is considered, several types of kinship can be distinguished:

Depending on the angle, from the point of view of which science kinship is considered, several types of kinship can be distinguished:

- Blood relationship is a relationship between people, which is not based on the principle of the common origin of people. Blood relationship can be of two types: direct, where one person comes from another; or lateral (collateral), where several individuals have one common ancestor. This kinship is a natural, "reference" kinship.

- Marriage kinship (property) is a relationship between people resulting from a marriage relationship. This kinship is social, since this type of kinship is built on the basis of the form of marriage accepted in society (society).

- Legal kinship is a relationship between unrelated people that arises as a result of the legal consolidation of this relationship (adoption, adoption), therefore, is determined by the social form. In the future, this relationship is equated to consanguinity.

- Spiritual kinship is a relationship equated to blood kinship that arose as a result of the church rite of baptism, therefore, this kinship is determined by the church.

- Ritual kinship is a connection between people that arises as a result of a ritual (twinning and others). It is determined by a social group; it is based not on consanguinity, but on social kinship.

- Psychological kinship is the rapprochement or separation of kindred / unrelated people based on their personal relationships (for example, comic kinship). This relationship is determined by an individual (ego).

Literature review. For the first time, L.G. Morgan drew attention to the need to study the terms of kinship. In his work "Ancient Society", the scientist first substantiated the idea that the system of kinship terms reflects the family and marriage relations that existed at the time of the appearance of this terminology, therefore, sometimes there are contradictions with modern family and marriage relations. [7,84]

L.G. Morgan believed that the study of kinship terms that are in conflict with real relationships can help to learn about the early stages of the history of family relationships.

B.K. Malinovsky believed that the nuclear family serves as the initial stage for analysis, since it is within the framework of this social group that the child acquires the skills of social interaction, develops his first interpersonal relationships. The individual gradually learns to react in a certain way to the actions of his family members, and also expects from them a certain response behavior, a response. Although, of course, his behavioral reactions may be of some individual nature, but since

the obligatory process of learning and socialization takes place in the family, as a result, his behavior will increasingly correspond to the cultural norms prevailing in this society. [3,24]

Methodology & empirical analysis. Society is a dynamic system, its structure, system, system, etc. change, which, consequently, is reflected in the language. In particular, related vocabulary also changes. This leads to the fact that it becomes more difficult to determine a specific type of relationship. Terms of kinship and properties will change, some will fall into disuse. Therefore, for the classification of kinship terms and properties, criteria are required according to which it will be possible to determine the type of kinship, as well as to conduct a comparative analysis of kinship terms and properties of different languages.

Based on the research of various scientists, mainly on the basis of the work of A. Kroeber and R. Lowy, a step-by-step classification was compiled for the analysis of related vocabulary. Eight relevant criteria were selected for the classification of terms of kinship and property - this is generation (generativity), gender, consanguinity / property, linearity / collaterality (bifurcation), polarity / reciprocity, relative age, lifetime.

Based on this classification, a comparative analysis was carried out, which makes it possible to detect similarities and differences between the system of kinship terms and properties of different languages (in this case, between the terminological system in English and Uzbek).

Results. All kinship terms and properties are considered from the point of view of relevance/irrelevance of these criteria in Uzbek and English. Kinship terms and properties are analyzed separately. For clarity, all terms are classified in the table based on criteria.

Terms of consanguinity

Generation (generativity)

In both Uzbek and English, the generation criterion is embedded in the term itself, since there are different terms for referring to relatives of any generation, both parents and children. Consider this criterion using the example of some terms denoting direct relatives:

Generation	Uzbek		English	
	gender		gender	
P (parents)	Male	female	male	female
4	Бобонинг бобоси	Бувининг бувиси	Great-great- grandfather	Great-great- grandmother
3	Катта бобо	Катта буви	Great- grandfather	Great- grandmother
2	Бобо	Буви	Grandfather	Grandmother
1	Ота	Она	Father	Mother

The Uzbek and English languages have a very developed system of kinship terms based on the criterion of generation (generativity): there are terms denoting both direct kinship and collateral (lateral) based on this principle; hence this criterion is relevant for both languages.

1. Gender. This criterion is fundamental for both Uzbek and English languages. In Uzbek all kinship terms are based on this principle, without exception. Currently, the following terms are used, based on the criterion of gender in Uzbek: mother, father, daughter, son, and others. .

In English, as well as in Uzbek, this criterion is relevant, but with the exception of one term: cousin; and also here you can include the term twins, but usually I add brother / sister to the term twin, for the gender indicator, and the term twin separately is usually used in the plural: twins. [10.23]

In English, gender-based terms are uncle, aunt, grandfather, grandmother, and others. The term cousin was borrowed from French, and by origin this term is Latin. In Latin, this term had a very narrow meaning. The Latin "consobrinus" literally means "mother's sister's child". The term was formed from com- "together with" and "sobrinus" (derived from "soror", meaning "sister") - "maternal cousin/cousin". Even the Romans, this term acquired a broad meaning: "the child of an uncle or aunt; as well as first-generation cousins/sisters."

"Consobrius" became "cousin" in Old French. In the 13th century, this term passed from French into English, but over the years its meaning has changed. For example, the term had the broad meaning "kinsman or kinswoman" ("relative/relative or kinswoman"). Shakespeare also used the term cousin to refer to a nephew/niece in *Much Ado About Nothing*: "How now, brother! Where is my cousin, your son?"

Since the 17th century, this term has been used to refer to a relative descended from a common ancestor, but along a different line.[15.56]

In addition, the terms "first cousin", "second cousin" and so on previously existed. "First cousin" is a term for an uncle's or aunt's child. "Second cousin" is a term used in relation to the child of a cousin/cousin of a father or mother.

2. Blood relation/property. Both in Uzbek and in English there are terms for designating both consanguinity (kinship by blood) and for designating property (kinship by marriage). Different terms used to denote kinship by blood and by marriage. For example, in Uzbek: она – ўғай она, ота – ўғай ота, ўғил – ўғай ўғил, etc.

In English: mother - mother-in-law, father - father-in-law, son - stepson, etc. However, in Uzbek the system of property terms is more developed than in English. (11.34)

3. Linearity/collaterality (bifurcativity). Both English and Uzbek are characterized by linearity (the distinction between direct and lateral lines of kinship). This means that for relatives along these two lines there are separate different terms, a bifurcation (bifurcation) of terms. For example, in Uzbek it is a ўғил - набира - чевара; она - буви – катта буви- and so on.

In English, this is daughter - granddaughter - great-granddaughter and so on. Previously, the criterion of collaterality (differentiation of alters (relatives) along the lines of father and mother) was one of the fundamental terms for the terms of kinship and property in both Russian and English. This can be seen in the kinship terms used to refer to uncle and aunt, where two different terms existed for uncle, and the same terms were used for both male and female aunt. That is, there was a bifurcation (bifurcation) of kinship terms. For example, in the Uzbek language, the term amaki was used to designate a paternal uncle, and toga for a maternal uncle. While paternal and maternal aunts, as well as paternal and maternal uncle wives, did not have special terms in the language, but were denoted by derivatives of the names of uncles: amma - paternal aunt (father's sister) and also the wife of paternal uncle kelinoia lines; hola is the maternal aunt and also the wife of the maternal uncle kelin oyi.

In English, there were also similar terms for uncle and aunt, based on the criterion of gender: fædera - father's brother, suhtor-fædera, suhtor-ge-fædera - mother's brother. However, in English there were different terms for both paternal and maternal aunts: "mōdrige", "moddrige" - mother's sister, "faðu" - father's sister. The modern English term "uncle" was borrowed from French, but the origin of the term is Latin, from the Latin "avunculus", which was formed from the Latin "avus" ("grandfather", "ancestor"), but the term "avunculus" was used mainly to refer to mother's brother (maternal uncle). When the word uncle was borrowed from the French by the English in the 13th century, it already meant only the brother of mom and (or) dad (paternal or maternal uncle), and this term was also used to refer to the husband of an aunt.[7.85]

The modern English term "aunt" also comes from the French language, which in turn is from the Latin word "amita", which was used to refer to the father's sister.

At present, in modern Uzbek and English, all these terms are no longer used, since the process of simplifying the system and merging terms has gone through.

Today, Uzbek speaking people actively use only words related to the closest blood relationship: mother / father, son / daughter, brother / sister, uncle / aunt, nephew / niece, grandson / granddaughter, grandmother / grandfather. Of what was previously called property (another gradually forgotten word, meaning kinship not by blood, but through marriage), in addition to husband and wife, only the already mentioned mother-in-law and son-in-law are used, and less often mother-in-law and daughter-in-law.

First of all, it speaks of the changes taking place in our life and culture. The huge Uzbek family with a complex hierarchy of relationships and fixed roles has been reduced to a small cell of society,

consisting of parents and their children and (as a rule, more often already coming) grandparents. And somewhere on the periphery - parent brothers and sisters with their children. [9.54]

The greater use of the words mother-in-law and mother-in-law compared to father-in-law and father-in-law indicates a more active role of women in family affairs, no matter positive or negative. The existence of various anecdotes, stories associated with the terms mother-in-law and mother-in-law also plays a role here, moreover, these stories mostly have negative connotations.

The conservatism of the Uzbek language is manifested in the fact that it reflects all these social changes, but with some delay. For example, it does not completely discard obsolete vocabulary, but stores it in a passive vocabulary as a slightly blurry memory of a relatively recent past - a kind of collective subconscious.

After all, for example, the words that bind people through baptism have returned: the godfather and godson, godmother with goddaughter.[8.43]

4. Polarity/Reciprocity. For English and Uzbek, the criterion of polarity is relevant. Polarity is based on the principle that two people are needed for a relationship, and two different terms are used to name these people. For example, in the Uzbek system of kinship terms, there are polar relations between the terms husband - wife, father-in-law - mother-in-law and others.

And in English, for example, these are the following pairs of polar terms: husband - wife, sister-in-law - brother-in-law, and so on.

5. Relative's age. This criterion is not relevant for either the English or Uzbek systems of kinship terms, since the relative's age relative to Ego does not affect the use of the property term in relation to this relative.

In Uzbek and English, Ego refers to a relative by marriage using the same term, both to a person older and younger than himself. After all, the main criterion is their position in relation to each other, the type of their connection. [9.32]

Conclusion. Briefly we conclude our ideas in this field, comparing modern terms with their predecessors, as well as identifying current trends based on a sociological survey, an increasing desire for linearity, rejection of bifurcation (delimitation) and polarity (the presence of a pair of terms opposed to each other) was noticed. This means that the system of kinship and properties is gradually being simplified, and terms are merging. Consequently, for the members of these societies, it is no longer relevant to distinguish between one or another relative. For example, the distinction between the terms denoting uncle, along the line of the father and the line of the mother in English and Uzbek. Or the tendency in the Uzbek language to merge the terms of property, currently separated along the line of husband and wife.

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5 ЖИЛД, 3 СОН

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